

The Family and Social Change in Xiamen City: An Anthropological Study of the Siming District

ZINGA Christian Amandin¹

¹ Department of Anthropology, School of Social Development, East China Normal University (ECNU), Shanghai, China

Accepted August 30, 2021
Published September 02, 2021

*Corresponding Author:
ZINGA Christian Amandin
christian.zinga86@yahoo.com
zchristianamandin@yahoo.fr

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5389823>

Pages: 112-132

Funding: None

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
ZINGA Christian Amandin
(2021). The Family and Social
Change in Xiamen City: An
Anthropological Study of The
Siming District. *North American
Academic Research*, 4(8), 112-
132. doi:[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.5389823](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5389823)

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This ethnographic research addressed the city transformation and social change in a Chinese city. The case study focuses on Siming district. The Siming district is an old and contemporary city center of Xiamen (Amoy) city, the second capital of Fujian province. It can be identified as a major city center and a global center. The study aims to develop the specific perspective of urban anthropology about urban transformation and social change in a Chinese city in this period of globalization. According to the Seventh Population Census in 2020, cities accounted for 63.9% of China's total population. Over the previous few decades, the China's urbanization rate has been gradually rising, and it has put it higher compared to some Asian, African cities, and European cities. The research has explored the urban structure of the city, including the cultural and social system. Furthermore, the study examined crucial urban theories and scholars from the Chicago school with different perspectives on urbanization and urban life. [Louis Wirth \(1938\)](#), as well as [Setha Low \(1999\)](#), examines contemporary patterns of the urbanization study. This study shed light on particular characteristics of urban phenomena in Xiamen city but more particularly in the Siming district as an urban center. Since the Cultural Revolution in 1974, the economic reform from 1978s to 1979s, the pattern of life in entire China has been changed with a particular emphasis on the local culture, which has been influenced by the global urban culture and the Siming district in Xiamen city is not an exception. Moreover, these changes have brought some new aspects of life and patterns to life of the Siming district's urban residents. The Siming district's urban development and social change in this study have been studied in the light of globalization as it transitions from traditional and modern to the global state. The study examines the historical, social transformation of Xiamen city in general and the Siming district in particular through urban life, the global society, urbanization as well as urban families, by focusing on the urbanization as well as particular structure of the Siming district. The study also looks at the Chinese social system and it provides a history of Xiamen city and observations on China's structure between traditional and global phenomena about urbanization. Further, it also discusses the urban life

characteristics in the Siming district. Large numbers of immigrants from different parts of China and others countries have swelled Xiamen's population resulting in unique aspects of change. The Siming district, as an urban space also shares many similarities with other districts of Xiamen city, with other China's cities with foreign cities through the modern way of life. There is also the predominance of the new development of foreign cultures such as fashions, music, foods, education, etc., through the presence of immigrants and tourists.

Keywords: CHINA, XIAMEN, CITY, SIMING DISTRICT, FAMILY, SOCIAL CHANGE.

1. Introduction

This ethnographic research used information that has collected from the Siming district as a fieldwork site in the Chinese city of Xiamen to show how urban development and social change affect people's lives and cultures. However, this section will address the specific changes that have been happened in Siming district's family, more especially in women's status. When it comes to marginalization, segregation, or discrimination, women are always the first to be victims. Their role and status in society, whether in China or elsewhere, has always been neglected. However, today, although this thinking about women has changed, there are still women who continue to experience this gender discrimination in other areas such as education and the employment market. Furthermore, when it comes to the changes, women are also the first to get along with because, in urban spaces such as the Siming district, women are more urbanized than men. This is what I am going to develop in the following lines argue about the women education, women and employment both in tradition and modern Siming district because the study has been limited to the case of Siming district and it is surrounding in Xiamen (Amoy) city.

2. Materials and methods

The family and social change

Families are essentially about solidarities, and these are created, and pursued through blood ties, marriage and intimate relationships such as parent, child, grandparent and grandchild (Crow 2002:32). In this twenty-first century, there are both continuities and diversities in the forms and experiences of families. The notion of families and the lived experience of families remain an enduring one for everyday human existence, memories of the past, and anticipations of the future (Silva and Smart 1999). Families also are premised upon notions of kinship and assumptions about obligations and responsibilities between relatives and intimate partners, all of which constitute an accepted part of what we should do in families (Finch and Mason 1999: 300).

There is a large body of historical and contemporary work on social change, social traditions and social cohesion that illuminates the continuities and diversities in the lives of families (Durkheim 1976; Weber 1978). Before the industrial revolution, families were bound together by necessity and tradition. Kin, family,

and neighbors worked together to improve the chances of survival. Often lives were brief bleak, but relationships offered intimacy and support that tented to concentrate on the survival of children and other forms of family members. With industrialization, changes in the organization of families, especially the separation of paid work and home, made possible new forms of privacy and an enhanced focus on intimacy in the immediate family grouping. However, I have noticed that this kind of life is still presents among the inhabitants in some areas of the Siming district.

The family in China's context

Family, called (*Jiā* or *Jiātíng*) in Chinese Mandarin, is a simple and a complex concept. The family history is complex and varies from individual to individual or from one society to another. Quite often, the answer to the question “what is a family” Is like for example, In traditional Chinese society, family was another name, for a patriarchal clan, including not only its current members but also its consecrated and revered ancestors in the clan halls, a collection of feudal orders and ethical codes between relatives, based on Confucian doctrines. In contemporary China’ society, the meaning of the family may vary from person to person. From politicians such as the former leader of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), Mr. Yao Bang Hus says that family, rather than the individual, is the “basic cell” of the society. In the view of administrators, a family is a household within which a group of people lives at a given time for resident registration or census (Xuewen Sheng, 2004).

Mr. Chen Xiao has given some statements about urban family and social change according to his point of view:

“According to me, a family needs parents (husband and wife, and children) to be a perfect family. Not much, because the family structure cannot keep up with the social and cultural changes, so it has little impact. The family’s structure in Xiamen city does not represent our family core because the family’s structure is uneven.

Yes, I can say that there is a big difference between previous family and family of today. Living standards have improved, money has been spent better, buildings have become taller, and roads have improved.

Yes, it has a significant impact. If there are more people, you can make money. Living standards can be improved. There is a place to eat, drink and play. Urbanization is brought about by development and has little to do with the family.

Yes, it is. Urban women are the family organization and have one-third the right to choose. Yes, it is. After the higher education qualifications, I am around 30 years old, and I have to have a minor social status. Most of them are over 35 years old before they get married because it is hard to find a husband.

Yes, the kinship of Wufu is very fundamental in our society because it is a custom here. We have several activities together every year. I think a significant change has been made; the road is better, wider and cleaner. The city is several times broader, there are more people, and there are many more races here today in Siming district. ”

The urban family, as always, is one of the most representative institutions of urbanization in developing countries because it is necessary first to draw attention to some.

Contrary to rural society, urban society has many patterns of family structure. Family in China’s city in general and particularly in the Siming district differ in character from other societies on the globe, especially from that in Africa societies, which comprise social structures that lead to cohesion with family and social relations in the society. The most common pattern of family structure in the Siming district is the nuclear family. It has been influenced by the urban life, leading to changes in structure, function, or social environment; for example, modern intermediary that take place in the house, apart from those which increase and multiply intermediary modern communications. However, there are similar approaches between different family trends in the society even though the social and economic frameworks impact family trends in the city. More so than the rural family, the urban family has been affected by cultural and social change. Therefore, the absorption of norms has a connection with the urban life. An individual finds himself in a non-family relationship in the city.

Social and family relations of the Siming district are characterized by change and urbanization. The system of family structure has more impact on social-cultural organizations and the change norms have become very important in choosing a partner for life. Bearing social effects upon urban structure, the Siming district’s woman fortune in marriage is influenced by her level of education and to her traditional skill in cooking and housekeeping. The Siming district’s women are traditionally responsible for daily decision-making, and often have an input in determining some significant purchases.

Wang Li, 59 years old, have related that:

“In this contemporary Siming district’ society, we Chinese (women) seem to become more urbanized than men. Me for example, I spend time at home more than my husband. And I have more access to the television to the radio, where sometimes I turn into foreign broadcasts or watching foreign television, thereby learning about culture of others countries, especially about the foreign lifestyles, family to compare. Thus, I may say I (have been more socialized with) absorb the global culture which has gradually become evident in my lifestyle such as the dressing code, food taste, meals, and vocabulary. However (despite modernization), women still spend more time on household activities than men. In some way, I maintain my traditional aspects of culture, such as wearing the traditional clothes, rings.”

Despite what Wang Li said, I can understand that some Siming district's family has to function according to the Chinese traditional families' rules, which enforce aspects of culture such as dress code when working, shopping, talking in public places, eating or when receiving a guest in their respective home.

According to this research, the Siming district has many global aspects of the family regarding wedding celebrations. It also has many wedding halls where women and men wear clothes similar to that of foreigners. Women can dress the red color clothes, and men can dress in any color of a vest. Thus, the family can take on more- or less-traditional roles depending on the social situation, and such multiple patterns of life become a phenomenon within the family structure today.

In the modern Siming district, most urban characteristics have changed from before due to social interaction between individuals. They merge into the requirements of urban life and the complexity of city society. Hence, the young generation of Siming district can get married later in life at the age of 28 or 30 years old after graduation from the University, necessary for urban life. However, when they stop education from Middle school and do not attend University, they can get married early at the age of 22 years old. That means the urban family influences different systems, affecting social relations as well as social roles. However, some institutions besides the family have allegedly played a significant role in the education of children.

Kinship systems still play an essential role in the Siming district culture. I have observed that the presence of foreign from Asian, African, American and Europeans influence much in the Siming district where College and University students are seen to interact among themselves in college parks, or gardens, coffee shops, restaurants, bars, clubs etc. to establish a friendship that might lead to the union in marriage, which signifies a change in the patterns of life in the Siming district. In this way, I can say that higher education institutions such as Xiamen University in the Siming district have mainly contributed to the construction of families.

I also had seen that the Siming district people have many relations with different groups like friends, kin, and local communities. One can be a member of different associations through connections with friends, classmates, co-workers and neighbors. Therefore, an urban person has different roles in the urban environment. A place such as Siming district, social relations among relatives are not as strong as in rural areas: this is due to the differences in the social systems.

Xu Yue, 37 years old, an immigrant from Hunan, argues that:

“I have been lived in rural region for 14 years, in the urban area for eight years in China. I come from a county in the Hunan Province, the south of China. Before I move to the city for my higher education, I had been living in the rural areas. So I have lived both in the rural and the urban areas in China. Now I can compare the two different lives in two different places. The comparison can be based on the life

experiences in Hunan and Fujian province, more particularly in the Siming district, not in other places because I am only familiar with these two places.”

The places are beautiful and peaceful. The breath is sweet. I had usually gone to the crystal river to swim all afternoon when I was young in my village. People are staring at the blue sky when they are swimming. The sky is so blue that the people feel that their minds are open to the sources of peace. In contrast, in the city of China, for example, at the Siming district where the Xiamen University is located, the atmosphere is so good. However, the only problem is that if I want to swim, I have to go to the natatorium to pay money. It makes me feel uncomfortable.

People, mainly from the same village, know and familiar with each other. They kept a good relationship, communicate with others by words, and help each other. I can remember that my family often exchanged delicious food with our neighbors, and we shared good food. The boys or girls from the same village are always a perfect partners and friends. The friendship is a sweet memory. Contrary in the city, people may not know their neighbors unless they are from the same corporations. There are some scandals such that one person has been in death for many days, but his neighbors did not know he had died. Such things would never happen in rural areas. China is in the transition. People move from other places to another, a constant movement place, searching for the job and changing the job frequently. People live in the same community just because they buy the house from the same real estate developer. The methods to earn money in the rural and urban are different, she adds” (Xu Yue, 37 years old).

The arguments of Xu have clearly illustrating the notion of solidarity developed by the French sociologist [Emile Durkheim \(18-1917\)](#), which opposed to the mechanical solidarity and organic solidarity. He refers the notion to mechanical solidarity to mutual relations based on resemblance, similar values and traditions, shared rituals, and symbols, a common belief. This type of solidarity exists among rural dwellers or ancient society (*Jiù shèhuì*). Contrary to organic solidarity, he describes it as the social order is based on individual differences, which are common in modern society (*Xīn shèhuì*), i.e., urban spaces. Such solidarity is based on a dynamic division of labor, in which many different workers specialize in many different professions. People depend more on one another to meet various needs. In such a model of solidarity, he saw the prospect of greater equality of choice for all members of society through this dynamic division of labor. Emile Durkheim gives consideration to the social structures of the city, social solidarity as well as the bond between all individuals within a society ([E. Durkheim 1858-1917:65](#)).

It should be noted that the two models of solidarity developed by E. Durkheim can also be in the Siming district because I have noticed that within the community of the Siming district, despite this period of modernization, globalization, the community still sharing some specific values and traditions. The social organization of the inhabitants of the Siming district is still based on life in society, kinship even if the individualist begins to settle among the population, solidarity, and mutual aid of which E. Durkheim, still

visible within the community of Siming district. That is means the social ties have not yet disappeared, still urban spaces such as the Siming district. However, the “ties organic solidarity” described in these societies derives from the division of labor. When there is a division of labor, everyone must depend on others to perform their work. This interdependence of roles generally creates solidarity that retains much of the bond and sense of community found in small rural societies. This interdependence can still find in urban spaces among the community of the Siming district.

- **The marriage rights**

Urbanization has affected attitudes, role perception, and behavioral patterns regarding marriage. China’s government permits a family to have two children. Despite this, men with one than more wives are not existed in the Siming district, but as economic growth considerably, made easy for the young generation today to have one wife and more girlfriends. It is can simply be considered due to the impact of modern culture, which can destabilize the family structure.

“In our traditional China’s society (*Jiù zhōngguó shèhuì*), our parents play an important role in our decision to marry. We should find a pattern for us to marry, whether you like the pattern or not; and even though you did not love or do not meet your marriage partner before, you must just accept the wishes of the parents.” However, nowadays, in this modern society (*Xīn shèhuì*), the role of parents about arranged marriage (*bāobàn hūnyīn*), for us has become secondary because, with the spread of education and the increasing economic independence over the last decade, this traditional role of our parents has been changed. We now, especially the young generation, enter marriage by our own free choice, what we called (*Zìyóu liàn'ài*). It is quieted difficult to find these kinds of family in our society today, even though parents arranged marriage for us, it cannot work because we can decide to accept the offer of our parents. That is why today in our Xiamen, especially in the Siming district because you can see that women can get married with foreigner men even though parents are opposed to the union, they can still get married to others nationalities.”

I have observed that the degree of freedom of the young generation of the Siming district to choose where, when, whom to be married with, varies according to the level of education, socio-economic status, age and gender. They have more freedom than the older generation regarding the choice of their marriage partners. For many women today, the ability to choose when and with whom they shall married is particularly significant matter because the previous generation of women got married in accordance with their parent’s wishes.

When I questioned the group of some old generation women about what would happen if you rejected the candidate chosen or proposed by your family? They all replied that: “There is no way to reject what parents arranged for you. You must accept it (*Zhè shì bìxū de*) because in our Chinese traditional culture (*Zhōngguó chuántǒng wénhuà*), we must obey our parent’s decisions, whether it is good, for your life or not.”

Qing, a 68 years old woman for example, claims that:

“Like many of my classmates, I also plan to attend college when I was graduated from the high school, but things turned down for me because my parent was not able to pay my school bills and my younger sister at that time. Instead of staying at home, I just applied for a job to support my family, but I go to see my friends at the University. At that time, my point of view toward getting marriage was that I have to choose my future husband by herself. I think like if parents choose a husband for me “one day my parents will leave this world, and if we follow their choice or their rules about marriage it will be difficult for us because we are the one who will stay with the man they have chosen for us when they die. Who will suffer?” How about the divorce? Because of the man’s behavior cannot cope with mine, we will divorce and I will be sad, that is not fine. We first need to make ourselves happy before any other person; we cannot please our family and displeased ourselves simply because we have to respect the tradition or the culture.” I had long-term projects. Qing hinted that it is better to get married to an educated and decent man with initiative and desire to work. I thought that my happiness was an essential than obeying the aspirations of the older generation to marry a husband with a title and blue blood, evoking a sense of contemporary independence.

By the time I got married, however, my ideas had begun to fall more with my father's concerns. I explain how I finally chose my husband. My father’s priority was that I could marry a man from his lineage (Xuètǒng) and the same village because they do not want us as their daughter to go far from them, but I was not interested in the man chosen by my family. I had been in love with one young man from another village for a long time, but my mother was fiercely opposed to him, so I ultimately chose to pursue the relationship. When I approached the age of 27, an age, which considered as old enough to get married in China, I finally decided within couple of months to marry the man I love, although he was from another city. My choice was not the best one according to my family testimony, but one that was acceptable because they were able to verify that he was of elite rank.”

That is to say nowadays, girls do not choose their marriage partner based on their parents' preferences but according to their preferences. It does not mean that parents have lost their responsibility, or power in the marriage issue of their daughter because some family still maintains this thought.

- **New social organization**

The organization in a typical China’s family also becomes different from what was in the past, and Siming district is not an exception. Formerly, the men have not total control over his family. A woman does not need to have her beloved husband’s permission to travel abroad. Ma Quan Quan is one of those women staying out of their matrimonial home, precisely in Cameroon, for business. She lives there already about ten (10) years without her beloved family.

Ma Quan Quan claims that:

“Wǒ jīntiān xiǎng qù nǎlǐ zuò shìqíng jiù qù nǎlǐ. Bù xiàng yǐqián yīyàng, nǚrén zhǐ néng zài jiālǐ zhàogù jiāntīng, zhàogù háizi. Wǒ chūmén zuò mǒu shì zhīqián bù xūyào qǐngqiú wǒ zhàngfū de xǔkě. Zài lǎo zhōngguó de shíhòu shì zhèyàng, nǚrén bùnéng suǐbiàn chūmén.”

In recent years, a growing sense of individualism in some segments of society, more particularly among the educated young people, has been noted. For example, through such communications, indirect connections may be made with other communities, which may reduce the level of socialization within the family or local community. However, many Siming district's people keep a tribal mind, remaining proud of and loyal to their blood. Thus, in the case of family structure, the Siming district individualism is different from African individualism. So, individualism in Xiamen society works within the family and the general environment due to external factors such as facilities of communication.

In the modern Siming district, many educated young couples prefer to buy their own separate households rather than moving in with their parents. The 1970s, educational differences between men and women have narrowed, and this has resulted in role sharing and joint decision making between the younger generation couples. However, the husband still plays a central role in family life. In general, the freedom of women and wives is a general phenomenon: urban women under the age of 28 tend to have more modern attitudes towards life. While even though changes have impacted family life, older urban women are not more reluctant to give up their traditional values.

One of my respondents named Zhou, states that:

“Most of China's urban families, in general, are becoming more and smaller, and Xiamen's Siming district is not an exception. The members of the urban families have become more autonomous, in particular because the families have lived in the city for a long time and acquired new different names. There is also some use of foreigner names by those who have been to school (educated). However, up to the present, names have largely been the same in this part of China.”

My observation is that urbanization has had more negligible effect on family life in China than theorists previously predicted it would be because family and kinship continue to be very crucial factors in the Siming district's resident's life and this is at all levels of society. Thus, the characteristics of the urban family, particularly the size, have come to resemble the countryside (Peil and Pin 1984:182). Family life in urban areas has become less cohesive, but children are still regarded as highly in terms of their role as an economic asset in the city as they are in the villages. It is because they will generate family income through contributing labor in their work, which can generate income for the family.

Many changes that have happened in the Siming district affected family structure. Changes in family structure common to every city have been profoundly influential at all levels of the social hierarchy. However, changes in the Siming district life are not entirely the same as those in other cities of China. The Siming district's

families and community structures still have characteristics which do not differ from some Africa cities, particularly from families in the Central African Republic. It is because they have strong social links with neighbors, particularly in homogenous areas where most of inhabitants have moved to the city from the same community. A strong relationship among the family members can be observed within the city.

The impact of urbanization on the Siming district families is shaped and given unique character by specific cultures. Studies of the impact of modernization and social change on the family patterns in Siming district' societies reveal that the extended family was still the general pattern, with only the 'urban educated class' forming nuclear families. It was most frequently found in towns and cities. The economic condition and lack of education were the main factors responsible for the prevalence of extended family on a modest scale in cities.

Despite all this, traditional values are still considered to be strong among people even if it can be argued that urbanization results in refurbishing of cultures. However, another said that "city life has become complicated, having an adverse effect on interpersonal relations and co-operation between people because most of them are just busy with their job, business and do not have time to be entertained. This shows that modern changes brought by urbanization have, in some ways, negatively impacted the family. It can be seen as the result of factors such as unemployment, lack of certainty in their lives.

Women and social changes in the Siming district

From the reform period until today, the status of women in China's cities have been changed and the Siming district is not an exception. Women's growth in society has been helped by local culture and a global culture. Given the significance of hegemony in shaping culture's perceptions of women's roles, such cultural innovations alone will undoubtedly be inadequate to compel significant reform (1998:106). Despite this, the man remains the households head. However, the spread of the new global society has impacted on urban communities such as the Siming district. According to this research, the modern media such as television, the internet, radio have impacted the family dynamics more, and in both urban spaces and rural areas across China today, and especially in the Siming district. That is why scholars, the majority of whom are women and many of whom are doing research on women's positions in society, their status, and rights, and their education, using a range of disciplines such as history, political science, sociology, and anthropology.

In considering the women's position in the Siming district, I first look at how women's roles have shifted from traditional to modern society, more specifically in urban spaces, and how the family status is one of the most critical factors in defining identity. Women's attitudes as well as culture and social structures, are not the same, but it differs from one place to another place.

The complexities of family relationships have evolved. During this ethnographic research, I discovered that in the past, the family was distinguished by the husband's authority and a patriarchal structure (*Fùquánzhì*

jiégòu), which has increasingly been replaced by the new family mode. The family is now characterized by what is known as freedom, the democratic and peaceful environment. In both urban and rural settings, husband and wife partnerships have become equal; male and female relationships have become equal in some respect. Mistreatment of wives or daughter in law is frowned upon in society. Women's integrity, education and job opportunities, and their values and practices, are now universally respected by their men and other members of the family in the Siming district. Generally in the past, women used to be in charge of all household jobs in China in general, and in the Siming district in particular. However, in most the Siming district households today, the husband and wife share some of these responsibilities and duties. Nowadays, they encourage and assist one another in their daily lives. That is to say, in China, vast numbers of families with deep emotional links are forming.

Women's education and changes

All over the world, education is seen as one of the essential factors of development. Generally, it is defined as the training of someone in a particular field of activity, collecting of intellectual, cultural, moral skills gained in this field by the individual or by a group of people. It is also an implementation of means suitable for methodically developing a faculty, an organ. In addition, Human education includes skills and cultural elements specific to a particular geographic location, specific historical period as well. That is why each place on this planet has its specific education system, with a role that traditionally devoted to the parents of children to take their children into the customs of adulthood, and usually increasing intervention by the government. Therefore, a country like China also has the national educational system.

However, in this study, to deal with women and its education changes, I was explicitly limited to the case study of the Siming district because it is our fieldwork site.

- **Women and education in traditional society**

In order to understand women' traditional education and its development, we must initially look at the relationship between traditional moral thinking and women's role in history.

The Tang Dynasty's most significant textbook about women was that of Song Ruoqian and Song Ruo Zhao's interviews on women. It encouraged women to live a life of chastity and obedience. The Song's explanation of the issue was more thorough and detailed than Ban Zhao's women's book (Precepts for Women).

In "The Chapter on Conducting Oneself," it says: "Being a girl, one must first learn ways of conducting oneself properly. The key to achieving this is maintaining one's purity and chastity, which would then bring one honor. Hence, do not look over your shoulder while walking; do not move your lips much while speaking; do not sway your legs while sitting; do not lift your skirt while standing; do not burst into laughter when feeling happy; do not shout when feeling angry. That which belongs within must be kept apart from that which is without, just as each person should stay in the company of their sex. Furthermore, do not pry about;

do not venture out; cover your face if you are out; be discreet if you must spy on others. Do not exchange names with any unrelated men, and do not get friendly with any unladylike women. Behave decently and only then you can be a good being” (Wong Yin Lee, 1995:4).

There were ten (10) essential concerns regarding women’ education with which old Chinese society (*Jiù Zhōngguó shèhu*, (old Chinese society)) exerted control over women during the Tang Dynasty.

- Housework skills;
- Food and wine appreciation;
- Modesty and politeness;
- Lessons in deportment and make-up;
- Reading and arithmetic;
- Appropriate ways of speaking;
- Fidelity and loyalty;
- No singing aloud;
- No gossiping; and
- Respect and help for the elderly.

To recapitulate, the Chinese society, for almost 300 years, had been founded on the belief that heaven is ‘Qian’ and the earth is ‘Kun.’ However, the male gender is represented by Qian (meaning bright or positive, cheerful), and the female gender is represented by Kun (meaning dark or negative). Men, one is told, should be assertive and women yielding, the former active and the latter passive. It had also become the yardstick by which the success of a woman’s education was crudely and arbitrarily measured (Wong Yin Lee, 1995).

During the past decades, there was a considerable discrimination between males and females in China’ education system, in which women were not allowed attend properly education such as attending school except males. There were so many reasons for doing so. This was linked with some constraints such as insufficiency of structure; the loss of the values is one of the fears linked to education of girls; early marriages, the economic reasons may also explain the low rate of females’ education in China in general and especially in the Siming district; poverty was a crucial factor in the girls’ education at the time. At this level, the family was compulsory to choose between sending a boy or a girl to school. Males’ education was seen as long-term investment by the family compared to that of the girl, which was seen as a waste of time and resources because in the traditional Siming district, the family did not understand the importance of females’ education. That is why most of the females were not allowed to attend school, but to stay at home for doing housework, taking care of children, and nothing else.

In her investigation of emerging patterns of service work in contemporary China, sociologist Amy Hanser (2005) looked at the changing perceptions of gender and sexuality. Women who were strong, physically robust and hardworking were depicted favorably during the Maoist regime. Other types of femininities are

seen in modern, market-driven China. Hanser looked at the variety of femininities employment in work service regimes. She surveyed three outlets in the Chinese city of Harbin in 2001-2002. In a state-owned department store, there were few attempts at the gender-based portrayal of female workers. She surveyed three retail outlets in the Chinese city of Harbin in 2001-2002. There was no effort at gendered exhibition of women staff in the state-owned department store. Uniforms were unisex and heavy. In the shop, there were older women than younger girls. The feeling was reminiscent of Maoist times. The selling was done by young, sexily dressed women in a wholesale or retail field selling cheap clothes to new rural migrants. There was also an undisciplined, hyper-sexualized culture. The concentration was on youthful yet disciplined femininity in the luxury private department store, the apex shopping. The young ladies have received physical and demeanor training. They were often shown to the male gaze, which was discriminating. In the various job regimes, class-code femininities were working.

Moreover, a group of men that I interviewed also recognized that females' education was like acquired. And Mr. Zhen Sheng, 74 years old, claims that: "the girls' education in the traditional era was equated with a loss of values; the fear of not being a "good wife and a good mother."

The Siming district' females who have not been to school in their entire lives were also interviewed. They lamented about not being to school before, the lack of education and say: "*wǒ méiyǒu wénhuà, méiyǒu dúshū*. That means: I do not have a culture; I have not been to school."

They expressed a sense of regret about not being to school or for not receiving proper education simply because they were economically and socially dependent on their beloved husband's efforts. Furthermore, this level of dependence puts them in a condition of social vulnerability concerning violence and knowledge of their rights. However, they cannot adapt themselves to urban life because it is quite hard for them to work out of their respective home.

- **Women and modern education**

Through this research, I have discovered that in contemporary China, female's education in general, and especially in the contemporary Siming district has been changed with the new reform into modern where everyone can go to school without any gender discrimination, except the family who does not have enough money to send their children to school. The new education system has helped Chinese females and those from the Siming district in Xiamen city, in particular, to adapt and improve themselves to urban life today than in the past years. Further, it has changed their way of life from a traditional manner to a modern way of life.

I have realize that nowadays, in the Siming district, whether it is education, qualifications, or job experience, it all plays a part in deciding the majority of those pursuing freedom's option of occupation. However, Females there are not only more optimistic and committed to their vocational ideas as a result of their business ventures, but they have also been motivated by the local government as well as the central

government, their families, and peers to bring their career ideas into motion. In addition, the local system is well set up to help them boost their quality of life, financial situation as well. The higher education is now more open to women than it has ever been. As a result of the region's renovation, the urban ecosystem is more unified, giving women more access to socio-educational facilities that can broaden their horizons. In the Siming district, women's education and training centers can be located. With the growth of global culture on this planet, the patriarchal ideology has somewhat disappeared in social practices after being fought in the past decades where females aspire for better access to health, education, and careers conditions as the same salary, but today, this patriarchal ideology has disappeared.

Some men, such as Mr. Chen, 54 years old, have affirmed that:

“The schooling of females is important for the modern society because, according to him, an educated girl has much more pity on her parents when they are poor or become old and that they can support them economically.” The reasons given are therefore more emotional than political.

In general, it has been said that: “To educate a man is to educate a person, and to educate women is to educate a whole nation.”

On this basis, society has everything to gain from discriminatory education, which helps to build stronger relationships, egalitarianism between men and women, and which allow women to take a very active part in socio-economic and political changes of a country. It also has been found that when a woman is educated, at least at an elementary level of education, it can have a positive impact on the social and economic life of the family, and the household. The future of a country obviously and above all depends on women and young people, without excluding men.

Therefore, I found that the change in education rates indicates a shift in women's opinions on the value of education. Many families are increasingly making sacrifices in order to ensure that their children complete high school. People in the Siming district believe that education is essential for obtaining a paid job with a guaranteed income and pension. In addition, they realize the potential economic benefits of higher education and metropolitan employment for women, particularly when successful, educated daughters utilize their earned money to assist their families.

Zhou has concluded about women's education that: From the beginning of the People's Republic of China, there was a change in the perception of women's education. Women began a new social life as well.

The change in the perception of women's education could be seen from the outset of the Republic. Nowadays, Chinese women in general and the Siming district have accesses to the same educational opportunities as males. They began a new social life as well; they have left their homes to participate in an open society in which sexual equality includes equal pay for equal effort, jobs. Additionally, there is a new specific provision that has been made for working women, especially those who get pregnant. According to the legislation,

women are entitled to 56 days' maternity leave with here full salary. Therefore, women are no longer at risk of losing their careers merely because they decide to get married and have children and when to start a family life. There is no more the concept of “*Fùmǔ jiào nǚ gěi shéi, nǚ jiù jià gěi shéi*”. According to Zhou, there is a significant difference between women of today and their predecessors.

In brief, I have seen how women's education in the Siming district has become a desirable objective and how education has benefited the state by supporting national gender and modernity paradigms.

3. Contemporary women of the Siming district and employment market

It says that the founding of New China put an end to the feudal marital and family system endured for several millennia. Independent marriage based on mutual love and families lives in which husband and wife are equal has become the mainstream in contemporary Chinese society (ancient history Encyclopedia).

- **Women in old Siming district and employment**

Like in many countries such as the Central African Republic (CAR), the history of local culture and the traditional education that distinguishes men from women seems similar. In the past years, most the women there also stayed at home, and their participation in the labor market, the workforce was just limited. While staying at home, women had many duties at the post, especially concerning the home and children. Thus, they had little free time. However, women had responsibility for housework, such as cleaning, cooking, and childcare. The house was the first place for family interaction.

- **Women in modern Siming district and employment**

Nowadays, China's women's social-cultural situation in general, and those in the Siming district mainly has been changed. It is due to the modern education and social policy which encourages them to go to schools. Women are receiving the same education as men since after economic, political, education reform (1978-79). Furthermore, they are encouraged to enter many different types of occupations. They now have and enjoy the same right as men by exerting the same job. It is what they called (“*Nán nǚ píngděng*”) meaning “male and female are all equal.”

The Chinese government has approved international pacts relating to economic, social, and cultural rights of women that deal with such attitudes today. Therefore, in terms of women's status in society, the Chinese system stipulates equal opportunity as a principal aspect of legal dispensation. The current status of Chinese women in general and the Siming district women, in particular, is now reflected in a significant diversity in ways of living. Some women have gained positions of management in a company or organization; numerous of them have become active in current administration, such as head schoolmaster, Secretary, etc.

They are now allowed to work outside of their matrimonial home as well as outside of their homeland without their husbands permission, and this may be considered as a new phenomenon in Siming district' society that

has happened in the last decades (2003). It has led to a mixing of the roles of women between the modern and traditional.

Most of the women there are doing business in order to have the freedom to choose the type of life they want to live, the type of work they want to take part in, also in order to escape from the men dominance; also, they have become less dependent to men for their marital needs. The participation rate of woman in the labor force has increased over the last few decades.

When I asked Zhai 69 years old: *Nǚ rén hái kào jìn nán rén ma?* Are there women who still lie on their husbands economically?

She responds that:

“Jīntiān wǒmen dà bùfèn de Zhōngguó nǚ rén bù yòng kào jìn nán rén le. Yīnwèi xiàndài de Zhōngguó nǚ rén dōu huì zuò shì, huì zìjǐ zhuànqián. Bù xiàng yǐqián de yīyàng. Shénme dōu shì nán rén, nán rén zuò de. (There is no woman who stays at home without doing anything in this contemporary Siming district. A part from those who are already retired).

“Wǒmen xiàmén nǚ rén méiyǒu zhèyàng zi, nǚ rén dōu fāzhǎn le, yǒu néng lì chūqù zuò shì. Bǐrú shuō, wǒ bùnéng tiāntiān jiào wǒ de lǎogōng gěi wǒ qián, yīnwèi wǒ yěyǒu gōngzuò. Érqǐě, xiàndài de nán rén bù xǐhuān lǎn de nǚ rén.”

“Jīntiān, dà duōshù fùnǚ wǎnhūn. Fùnǚ wàichū cānyù shì yī zhǒng xīn xiànxiàng, tāmen cānyù bùtóng de shèhuì jīngjì hé bùtóng de fúwù; fùnǚ de shēntǐ hé qínggǎn shǔxìng yǒushí huì xiànzhì tāmen zài jiùyè língyù de shēngchǎnlì. Wénhuà biàngé duì nǚxìng yǒu suǒ bāngzhù, yīnwèi tāmen xiànzài shòuguò gèng hǎo de jiàoyù, gèng yǒu shèhuì yìshí, duì hùliánwǎng jiāoliú biǎoxiàn chū xìngqù, yīncǐ xiànzài bèi rènwéi yǔ nánxìng yīyàng shì yánjiū xiǎozǔ de zhòngyào chéngyuán.”

The women of today do not appear to worry if their husbands leave them or not, probably because some Siming district women had their personal means, such as cash crops, while other women do not want to get married but preferred to attend school.

However, one male of 71 years old, named Jizhou Liu Yedao, observed and according to his personal point of view that:

“Women do not obey commands very well anymore.” However, some men also have no idea of how to put things in order in their families. Those are some tough men (*nian*). At the same time, men are frightened of their spouses being taken to court. Some of the women there are living in their old ways, while others are adapting to the new way of life.”

Mr. Liu went on and added that:

“Younger ladies, as well as some older women, are solely interested in wealthy men. They dismiss the ‘impoverished men’ as “rubbish” (Kàn bù qǐ). They used just to want guys who could give them money and take care of them and their children. Women wanted men who will purchase a house, a car, go shopping, enjoyable a trip.”

The women of the Siming district have also got a role in the domain of culture. They have overcome unfavorable conditions that have held them back, preventing them from exercising their role in artistic and literary creative movements and an information technology. Their presence in the field was intermittent. Some of them can be found in broadcasting, theatre or journalism, researchers, etc. Moreover, social backwardness in the sixties and seventies has also deprived many women of exercising their right to free expression artistic work.

Although the number of women working in every field has increased, some women are still significantly under-represented because of their level of education. It may be attributed to the fact that their participation in the labor force is relatively new and has only occurred over the last forty (40) years after the reform. In the field of information technology, for example, the 1990s saw the involvement of women in various forms. Women have also contributed to written journalism. Chinese women in general, and the Siming district in particular, are now working as men in different fields where they hold leading posts within the framework of exercising power and participation in education, political, socio-economic life because over forty years now, the Siming district is managed to attain several principal positions in several social-economic, as well as political fields including other fields.

Thus, in addition to the growing participation, women have more chances to occupy principal positions in public administration today. These posts include posts such as directors of departments, head of administration sections in the secretariat, heads (Dean) of colleges, director of the departments and principals of schools and institutions at all levels, heads of business departments, etc. Also, other occupations such as aviation, police and the armed forces, Siming district women can now drive a taxi, buses and trucks, etc. Additionally, nowadays, with the acquisitions of their higher levels in education, many of them are willing to work in other areas of public employment and in private employments.

I think there are some conflicts in women’s lives between her role as a mother and as a housewife, also her role as a professional or worker outside of her matrimonial home. In addition, there are many people have a positive attitude towards women who are working in many areas of life and types of jobs. However, it is not all individuals who are sharing these points of view concerning women in their everyday life. For example, their friends, aunts, sisters, daughters, etc.

Many young women who grow up under the patriarchal (*Fùquánzhì*) system of the Chinese city-state feel they are better off now since they can choose their jobs and marriages. These young women, who have been

brainwashed in state ideas and encouraged to look outside of the city they were born, consider the older generation to be antiquated in many ways.

Wang Lin is one of these women who claim that:

Today I have freedom in my life because I have the right (*Juéding quán, Shòu jiàoyù quán*) to choose what to do as job, with who to get married to.

The comparisons that need to be made between traditional “Jiù shèhuì” and modern “Xīn shèhuì” are that there has been an essential and considerable change that occurred in the lives of the Siming district. The woman’s status and role have been influenced by modern society, and they have gained the education at the global level like other women in this planet today. However, we also noticed that these changes put these women in some problematic situation because they do not know whether to perceive themselves as a modern or still a traditional woman.

Miss Yi, 67 years old women have also testified that:

“Zhè jiùshì yīnwèi xiàmén de fāzhǎn, shèhuì biàn gǎigé hěn kuài, Suǒyǐ jīntiān yǒu de nǚrén bù zhīdào tāmen shì chuántǒng de háishì xiàndài de. Yě shì yīnwèi měi gèrén dōu xiǎngxiàng měi gèrén yīyàng. Wǒ juédé yǒu yīdiǎn er Kùnhuò.”

It may be considered due to the rapid transformation of Xiamen’s Siming district as a Special Economy Zone (SEZ).

In the first half of the nineteenth century, [Christine Stansell \(1986\)](#) also conducted the first comprehensive study of the history of female roles in New York City. She argued that working-class women had more employment as a result of shifting economic conditions, and they shaped new ways of life in the parks, apartment blocks, gin rooms, and sweatshops.

Women have progressed from the domestic to the public domain, becoming household heads in some respects, using their children’s labor, forming working women’s societies, and participating in formal politics. This development posed a challenge to many middle-class women, who, unable to function due to cultural traditions, assumed the role of the nation’s moral guardians. Working-class women’s emergence as an economic, social, and political power questioned long-held conceptions of women’s “proper” position and “essential existence.” Working-class women formed a coalition that advocated for their rights and established a presence in the area. In Stansell’s words, they created small freedoms from large oppressions.

- **Professional occupations**

Many women today have earned degrees in higher education and vocational licenses. More surprisingly, and according to my survey is that the majority of married women in the Siming district today tented to be professional, educated women, such as high school teachers, university teachers, nurses, doctors, etc.

The most common professions for women are teaching, nursing, business, accounting, and administration. Women from the Siming district are now also a doctor. The few opportunities were available for professionals in Siming district. In the past years, more of the local teachers were Han. In one exceptional family, five of the seven children (three daughters' four sons) were all teachers: two of the daughters live and teach in the village, two live and teach elsewhere, and the son lives in the Siming district, and nearby.

- **Other occupations**

The proximity of Gulangyu to the Xiamen urban center, which is the Siming district, offers today additional opportunities for wage employment. Factory employment in the Siming district centers on the tourism industry, as Siming district is a significant destination for tourists visiting many cultural sites surrounding it. Many young people, especially young ladies, seek these opportunities.

- **Siming district Women and commuting**

One day when I was in front of KFC near Xiamen University waiting for a taxi, I saw that all of those who were waiting with me were all women. According to my informal survey, the majority of these ladies were on their way to work in search of jobs. Many of them also were out to go shopping. Therefore, I have learned that today commuting is a new strategy for the Siming district's women. That is to say, in Siming district, women have few choices for earning money. The funds raised through this initiative are frequently insufficient to meet the family's financial requirements. Illiterate women have few options. However, they work in businesses such as stores, restaurants. Married, unmarried, divorced, widowed, and single women, on the other hand, actually had a wide range of jobs. Most factories employed unmarried women because of their flexibility and lack of family commitments, pressures.

One of the things I noticed throughout my study about women is that when it comes for leaving their children with strangers or childcare, moms in the Siming district do not have the same worry as mothers in other places of the world. When traveling for work or conducting business outside of the country, the majority of these women testified that their mother or father-in-law is always there to look after their grandchildren.

Despite all this, what it should remember is that the percentage of women in the labor market has considerably increased today compared to the previous years. For example, only 43% of women are working in 1970, 61% in 2000, and 68.2% in 2019, is according to the Bureau of National Statistics.

4. Conclusion

This research has presented the specific changes that have occurred in the lives of the Siming district, such as family change, both women's traditional and modern roles and status in China's society, more especially in the Siming district. As anthropologists have long testified, social change in cultura and gender is an uneven, sometimes fragile process, with opportunities for individuals to increase their social rights and legal entitlements. The process of change that followed reform and opened the market to foreign investments, more

recently, globalization has resulted in a rising acknowledgment of women's rights in traditional Chinese cultural (communities') way of living across the Siming district. More recently, with the economy growth, global culture, and better transportation opportunities, the internet, technology have opened up new horizons for the younger of the Siming district, more particularly the young ladies, who strive to be educated, attractive, and confirmed in twenty-first-century ambitions to be equal to their fellow female on this planet.

Concerning education, it has been said that to educate a man is to educate a person and to educate a woman is to educate a whole nation. Based on this, society has everything to gain from teaching no longer about relationships and just helping to bring about changes in men who are more egalitarian and to establish between women, on the one hand, and which allows women to take a very active part in socio-economic and political of a nation.

It also has been says that when a woman is educated, at least at an elementary level of education, this reflects positively on the social and economic life of the family and the household. This family is inclined to send their daughter to school. So according to this research, I simply found that the problem of role, status and education of girls or women in China in general, and particularly in the Siming district in the old way of life was not a lack of political will. However, it is due to a problem at the way of thinking and traditional institutions such as Confucius institutes. Also, it was according to the traditional and cultural perspectives on women's position in the society that did see the impact or that wants to keep or maintained women under the domination of men and dependence on men as well in the name of tradition and culture.

References

1. Christine Stansell (1986). *Christine Stansell, City of Women: Sex and Class in New York, 1789–1860*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 1986; Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1986. xiv + 301 pp.
2. Emile Durkheim (1976). *The Elementary Forms of the Religious Life*. Allen and Unwin. 456 pages
3. Max Weber (1978). *Economy and Society. An outline of interpretive sociology*. Berkeley, CA. university of california press.
4. Louis Wirth (1938). "Urbanism as Way of Life." The University of Chicago. *American Journal of Sociology*.
5. Setha M. Low (1999). *Theorizing the City: The New Urban Anthropology* Redear Rutgers University Press, 448pp
6. Elizabeth B. Silva and Carol Smart (1999). *The New Family*. Sage publication Ltd. 185 pages
7. Wong Yin Lee (1995). *Women's education in traditional and modern China*. *Women's History review*. Routledge
8. Xuewen Sheng (2004) . *The Chinese families*. P.99

ZINGA Christian Amandin. Researcher, Department of Anthropology, School of Social Development, East China Normal University (ECNU), Shanghai-China

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

